

Accession Number: P565894

02 ago 2018

Patient ID: P32719

Optima CT660

Exam Description: BIOPSIA TC SCHELETRO

Report Dose

Series	Type	Scan Range (mm)	CTDIvol (mGy)	DLP (mGy-cm)	Phantom cm
1	Scout	-	-	-	-
2	Helical	I101.500-I284.000	4.75	117.18	Body 32
3	Helical	I150.000-I210.000	4.43	55.09	Body 32
4	Helical	I150.000-I210.000	4.43	55.09	Body 32
5	Helical	I150.000-I210.000	4.41	54.85	Body 32
6	Helical	I150.000-I210.000	4.41	54.88	Body 32
7	Helical	I150.000-I210.000	4.43	55.10	Body 32
8	Helical	I150.000-I210.000	4.43	55.10	Body 32
9	Helical	I150.000-I210.000	4.43	55.06	Body 32
10	Helical	I170.000-I192.500	4.13	35.87	Body 32

Accession Number: P565894

02 ago 2018

Patient ID: P32719

Optima CT660

Exam Description: BIOPSIA TC SCHELETRO

Report Dose

Series	Type	Scan Range (mm)	CTDIvol (mGy)	DLP (mGy-cm)	Phantom cm
11	Helical	I170.000-I192.500	4.14	35.93	Body 32
12	Helical	I170.000-I192.500	4.13	35.90	Body 32
Total Exam DLP:				610.07	